

Preface

Crops for the Future Research Centre (CFFRC) is a centre dedicated to research on underutilised crops for food and non-food uses. CFFRC research focuses on agricultural biodiversity to enhance agricultural systems and their sustainability, address changing climate, and improve food and nutritional security and economic well-being, especially of the poor.

The standard of procedures (SOPs) serve as the guidelines for data managers to collect and enter data into the database. The SOPs are found to be the best practices of data collection and data entry after many repetition of the activities through many different sources. The SOPs are practical for the latest version of the database (<http://35.192.29.140/cropbasev5/>). The data managers are advised to study and understand the whole database architecture before getting into the data collection and data entry activities.

Data collection SOPs were prepared by Knowledge Systems Theme team members:

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Guide on using the SOPs:

The SOPs were created for the focused data collection activities in the Global Knowledge Base for Underutilised Crops development. The document title represents the data collection activity which may help the data manager to seek the right SOP for the data collection purpose.

Related identifiers:

<http://cropbase.co.uk/cropbasev5/>

<https://github.com/CFFRC-KST/CFFRC-Global-Knowledge-Base>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3735694>